

PRACTICES OF USING VOCABULARY LEARNING STRATEGIES IN EFL CLASSES: GRADE 11 IN FOCUS

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The abstract-the main objective of this study was to assess the students' practice of using vocabulary-learning strategies in EFL classes. To achieve the objective of the study, the researcher used a mixed research design involving both qualitative and quantitative methods. Grade 11 students and respective English language teachers were participants in the study. 112 students for the questionnaire, 6 teachers for the interview, and 9 students for FGDs were selected as a sample using random, comprehensive and purposive sampling techniques respectively. Along this side, questionnaire, interview, and focus group discussions were the main data-gathering instruments. The closed-ended questionnaires were analyzed using percentage, mean, and standard deviation using a statistical package for social science students (SPSS) version 25 software, while the data obtained through open-ended questions, FGDs, and interviews were analyzed qualitatively using thematic analysis. Findings disclosed that social vocabulary learning strategies were frequently practiced; cognitive, memory and compensation strategies were medium practiced and utilized by the students whereas, meta-cognitive and affective strategies were least practiced by the students. Besides, the find of this study also depicted that students faced challenges like lack of practicing appropriate vocabulary learning strategies, shortage of vocabulary, lack of experience and lack of interest. Similarly, teachers' method of teaching, unclear instruction, little curriculum emphasis to train vocabulary learning strategies efficiently, too easy or the difficult nature of vocabulary, and the size and the complexity of the tasks were the external factors.

Index terms-practice, vocabulary, vocabulary-learning strategies

I. Introduction

Knowledge of word meanings plays a significant role in understanding a language. Hence, vocabulary instruction must be important for learners to use the instructed words meaningfully. One for this fact is that students learn and better practice when the students are actively reacted. Even if it is accepted that knowledge of vocabulary is one of the major keys for effective communication in language, most students do not know the relevant practices of using appropriate vocabulary learning strategies effectively. It is also particularly accepted that the knowledge of vocabulary is one of the main keys for successful communication in language because vocabulary words have the potential to express feelings, ideas, and emotions while communicating.

Thus, the one who should practice and use appropriate vocabulary learning strategies has been expected to communicate well by using the four skills integration. Using appropriate vocabulary learning strategies helped the people to equip in learning ESL in English. Therefore, to be an effective communicator, speakers should be rich in vocabulary (Harmer, 1991).

According to Hatch and Brown (1995), it is recognized that the students' practice of vocabulary learning strategies that the learners utilize has greater value on the success of their vocabulary learning. Appropriate vocabulary learning strategy has a great impact on achieving English as a second/foreign language education. Consequently, vocabulary is central to language and has great significance to language learners because words are the building blocks of a language since they label objects, actions, ideas without which people cannot convey the intended meaning i.e. while without grammar very little can be conveyed, and without vocabulary, nothing can be conveyed.

Nation (2001) further describes the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and language use as complementary: knowledge of vocabulary enables language use and, conversely, language use leads to an increase in vocabulary knowledge of strategies with the appropriate practice of vocabulary learning strategies.

However, students at Belay Zeleke senior Secondary and Preparatory schools still seem to have problems in the practice and using vocabulary learning strategies in EFL class in grade 11 in focus. In light of this, the purpose of this study was to assess the students' practice of using vocabulary learning strategies at Belay Zeleke Senior Secondary and Preparatory School in EFL class grade 11 in focus.

II. The Statement of the Problem and its context

Vocabulary is not explicitly taught in many second/foreign language classes because students are expected to learn new meanings by using different vocabulary learning strategies. These strategies are believed to equip the students with sufficient vocabulary knowledge. According to Beck and Mckeown (1985 cited in Abebe, 1997), vocabulary knowledge is considered as the 'cornerstone of literacy'. In line with, Nation (2001) also states that vocabulary knowledge is assumed to be a prerequisite to the performance of language skills. Hence, vocabulary knowledge should be a high priority goal for students, who aim to be autonomous and successful learners since without vocabulary there is no communication. In other words, vocabulary knowledge allows the learners to use the language in the way the students want because meaningful learning and teaching take place when there is the active involvement of learners in the language learning process that is supported by different appropriate use and practice of vocabulary learning strategies in EFL classes. In this regard, Schmitt (1997:215) also states:

One approach of facilitating vocabulary-learning practice in EFL class that has attracted increasing attention is vocabulary-learning strategies. Interest in vocabulary learning strategies has paralleled a movement away from a predominantly teaching-Oriented perspective to one that includes interests in how the actions of the learners might affect their acquisition of language.

Nonetheless, these days, most English language teachers in Ethiopia complain that many students do not have adequate vocabulary to improve their English language achievement. The inadequacy of the learners' vocabulary may result from their vocabulary learning strategies use and practice. According to Fan (2003), the inadequacy in lexical knowledge may hinder students' language proficiency development. Students may lack adequate vocabulary due to their inability to employ appropriate vocabulary learning strategies, which in turn, might make them lose interest in learning EFL.

There have been many global studies attempting to explore vocabulary-learning strategies. For example, a study conducted by Chich (2004) on "An investigation into vocabulary learning strategies used by students." The finding showed that cognitive strategies were dominantly used, but the minimum used strategies were the use of social strategies. Similarly, Sana (2013) conducted a study on "An investigation of the effect of developing learners vocabulary learning strategies lexical competence." The result indicated that EFL students use vocabulary learning strategies to a medium extent.

As evidence, there are also a few local studies on vocabulary learning. For instance, Setegn (2007) conducted "Investigates vocabulary learning strategies employed by Somali speaking students." According to his study, there is no statistically significant gender difference among learners in using vocabulary learning strategies except for cognitive strategies. Another researcher, Getnet (2008) studied "vocabulary learning strategies use among high and low achiever students in Gondar teacher college education." The finding shows that there was a relationship between vocabulary learning strategies use and language learning achievement. The more successful language learners (i.e. high achievers) use more vocabulary learning strategies than the less successful learners (i.e. low achievers).

However, the above researchers did not assess the students' practice of using vocabulary learning strategies at the preparatory level, and they have not seen the challenges that the students faced in the practice of using vocabulary learning strategies in the EFL classes at the preparatory level, but they claimed to explore the general vocabulary learning strategies at college and university level and identifying vocabulary learning strategies used by Somali speaking students in adult secondary school. Moreover, the above researchers did not touch the types of vocabulary learning strategies the students practice most and the least frequently, and the major challenges the learners faced in this regard.

The current researcher aimed to conduct this study by carrying out peer supervision to see the students' practice in EFL class and discussing with teachers who were teaching English in EFL class to assess what type of

vocabulary learning strategies the learners use and what major challenges faced while practicing vocabulary learning strategies. Due to these reasons, the researcher was motivated to assess the students' practice of using vocabulary learning strategies in EFL classes.

Basic Research Questions

To achieve the purpose of this study, the following research questions were proposed.

1. What are the major types of vocabulary learning strategies students use most and least frequently in the practice of learning vocabulary in EFL class?
2. What are the major challenges students faced while learning vocabulary using vocabulary learning strategies in EFL class?

III. Methodology

The major aim of this study was to assess the students' practice of using vocabulary-learning strategies in EFL classes in grade 11 at Belay Zeleke senior secondary and preparatory school. In this study, a descriptive case design involving both qualitative and quantitative approaches was employed. This method of research design is concerned with the present phenomena in terms of conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, relationships, or trends invariably.

a. The population of the Study

Belay Zeleke senior secondary and preparatory school is found in the East Gojjam zone in Amhara regional State. It is located about 265 km from Addis Ababa, 80 km from Debre Markos town, and 330 km from Bahir Dar. The school is selected as a study area for two reasons. To begin with, the researcher observed the problem informally in this school since the researcher has worked in this place. Second, it is convenient to get authentic, valid, and reliable data since the researcher is familiar with the teachers and other subjects of the study. Similarly, the sources of data were English language teachers and students at Belay Zeleke Senior Secondary and Preparatory School in grade 11 in EFL classes. In the 2020/21 academic year, 6 English language teachers were teaching of grade 11 and 448 grade 11 students found in the school. Thus, the population of the study were (6) EFL English teachers and 448 students in the same grade level. The reason to select grade 11 was that it was a grade level that students have learned for the preparation of higher education or university, and they have also expected to have a better potential to practice appropriate vocabulary-learning strategies in EFL class. Furthermore, the researcher believes that grade 11 students have a better understanding of the practice of vocabulary learning strategies than other lower grade levels students have.

b. Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Since it was difficult to incorporate the whole population in the study, the researcher decided to take samples from the subjects of the study. To select students from the total population of 448 in the study, the researcher used a simple random sampling technique. Therefore, 112 students were considered as a sample of the study. On the other hand, since the numbers of teachers were 6 and easily manageable, all grade 11 English teachers (6) were taken as a sample using a comprehensive sampling technique.

c. Data Collection tools

To collect the relevant data for this study, three types of data collection tools were used, namely; questionnaire, interview and focus group discussion. Questionnaires were used to answer the students' practices of using vocabulary-learning strategies in EFL class. The interview was prepared to assess the practice of the students' using vocabulary learning strategies and the difficulties they face practicing vocabulary learning strategies. Lastly, FGDs helped the researcher to identify what types of vocabulary learning strategies students used and the major challenges of using vocabulary-learning strategies the students faced in the practice of using in EFL classes particularly in grade 11 on focus.

Data Analysis Technique

To make the collected data more meaningful, the information collected from FGD, interviews, and open-ended items were analyzed thematically. On the other hand, the data which were collected through questionnaires were

analyzed quantitatively by using a statistical package for the social science students (SPSS) version 25 software. The quantitative data collected through close-ended questions have been entered into the computer and statistically described in terms of frequency in percentage, mean, and standard deviations.

IV. Data Analysis

4.1 Analysis of Students' Questionnaires

Table 1.

Students Practice of Cognitive VLS categories

No.	Techniques	No of participants	Responses					M	SD
			Rarely		Some times	Frequently			
			Never	Rarely	Some times	Frequently	Almost always		
		112							
1	Interpreting parts of speech of a new word	No	8	42	45	10	7	2.69	.95
		%	7.1	37.5	40.5	8.9	6.3		
2	Using word formation (prefixes, root, and suffixes)	No	10	19	20	61	2	3.23	1.04
		%	8.9	17	17.9	54.5	1.8		
3	Using word lists	No	19	10	49	10	24	3.22	1.16
		%	17	8.9	43.7	8.9	21.4		
4	Relating synonyms and antonyms meanings.	No	7	3.6	38	44	19	3.57	1.01
		%	6.3	3.6	33.9	39.3	17		
5	Saying a new word several times.	No	25	45	30	10	2	3.23	1.42
		%	22.3	40.2	26.8	8.9	1.8		
6	Writing a new word several times.	No	35	45	20	7	5	3.36	1.34
		%	31.3	40.2	17.9	6.3	4.4		
7	Taking notes in class in English.	No	4	10	37	53	8	3.43	1.65
		%	3.6	8.9	33	47.3	7.1		
Grand Mean								3.24	1.22

Keys: M: Mean, SD: Standard deviation

As shown in table 1, 44.6% of the participants replied that they rarely learned the new vocabulary by interpreting parts of speech of a new word to know its meaning. Besides, 40.5% of the respondents responded that they sometimes try to interpret parts of the speech of a new word. On the other hand, a small number (15.2%) of the respondents responded that they frequently practiced the same strategy by interpreting the parts of speech. This implied that the students' practices to learn vocabulary by interpreting the parts of speech were least implemented.

Item 2 revealed that most (56.3%) of the respondents responded that the students learned vocabulary by using word formation (prefixes, root, and suffixes) to know the meaning of a new word frequently practiced, whereas a quarter (25.7%) of the respondents answered that they rarely learned a new word using a word-formation (prefixes, root, and suffixes). Nonetheless, 17.9% of the respondents replied they sometimes practiced using word-formation. This indicates that the students highly practiced and learn vocabularies by using word formation (prefixes, roots, and suffixes) to know the meaning of a new word.

Regarding the same table item 3, depicted that nearly half (43.7%) of the respondents replied that they sometimes learned a new vocabulary using word lists. On the contrary, 25.9% of the respondents responded that they rarely practice using word lists when they discover the meaning of a new word. 30.3% of the participants reported that they frequently practiced word lists strategy when they discovered the meaning of a new word. This could be proved by the mean score (M= 3.22, SD = 1.16). From this, one could deduce that using word lists to discover the meaning of a new word was frequently utilized.

As seen table 1, item 4, illustrated that more than half (56.3%) of the respondents answered that the students frequently used to learn vocabulary by relating the words' synonyms and antonyms meanings, whereas few

(9.9%) of the respondents replied that they rarely used to relate the words' synonyms and antonyms meanings to discover the meaning of new words. This entailed that learners frequently used and practiced vocabulary by relating the words' and synonyms and antonyms meanings.

Item 5 displayed that the majority (62.5%) of the respondents reported that they rarely learned the vocabulary by saying a new word several times. Conversely, a small number (10.7%) of the respondents responded that the learners frequently practiced new words saying several times. we can notice that the students rarely practiced a new vocabulary by saying a new word several times.

As shown in table 1, item 6 revealed that the majority (71.5%) of the respondents reacted that they rarely learned vocabulary by writing a new word several times. However, only a few (10.9%) of the respondents answered that they frequently practiced a new word writing several times with a mean score ($M=3.36$, $SD = 1.34$). It can therefore be said that the students rarely practiced learning vocabulary by writing a new word several times.

Regarding the same table above, item 7 displayed that more than half (54.4%) of the respondents responded that they frequently learned the meaning of a new word by taking notes in class. Nevertheless, a small number (12.5%) of the participants responded that they rarely learned a new word by taking notes in class in English. This implied that taking notes in class was frequently used and determined as the most frequent practice under the sub-categories of cognitive strategies.

Table 2
Students practice using Memory vocabulary learning strategies

No.	Techniques	No of participant	Responses					M	SD
			Rarely		Some times	Frequently			
			Never	Rarely	Some times	Frequently	Almost always		
		112							
8	Studying the spelling and pronunciation a word	No	23	53	20	11	5	2.30	1.04
		%	20.5	47.3	17.9	9.8	4.5		
9	Guessing the meaning by analyzing any available pictures or gestures.	No	17	58	19	12	6	2.39	1.04
		%	15.2	51.8	17	10.7	5.4		
10	Using semantic maps	No	17	29	52	9	5	2.60	.98
		%	15.2	25.9	46.4	8	4.5		
11	Grouping (word association)	No	11	14	21	49	17	3.41	1.18
		%	9.8	12.5	18.8	43.8	15.2		
12	Visualizing the words form	No	7	22	33	40	10	3.21	1.06
		%	6.3	19.6	29.5	35.7	8.9		
13	Using new words in sentences and conversations	No	14	40	30	9	19	2.81	1.26
		%	12.5	35.7	26.8	8	17		
14	Using the vocabulary section (glossary)	No	22	14	20	42	14	3.10	1.33
		%	19.6	12.5	17.9	37.5	12.5		
		Grand Mean						2.83	1.12

Key: M =Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

As seen in Table 2, the result of the study in item 8 depicted that the majority (67.8%) of the respondents answered that they rarely learned vocabulary by studying the spelling of a word and its pronunciation to remember the meaning of a new word. On the other hand, 14.3% of the participants replied that they frequently practiced vocabulary by studying the spelling of a word and its pronunciation to remember the meaning of a new word with mean value ($M= 2.30$, $SD = 1.04$). However, 17.9% of the respondents responded that they sometimes

learned vocabulary by studying the spelling of a word and its pronunciation to remember the meaning of a new word. we can notice that students frequently practiced studying the spelling of a word and its pronunciation to remember the meaning of a new word.

Item 9 indicated that most (67%) of the respondents replied that they rarely learned vocabulary by guessing the meaning of a new word and analyzing any available pictures (gestures) while a small number (16.1%) of the participants frequently practiced guessing the meaning of a new word and analyzing any available pictures or gestures to learn vocabulary. From the above item 9, one can recognize that students rarely practiced learning vocabulary by guessing the meaning of a new word and analyzing any available pictures or gestures.

Table 2, item 10, revealed that only a few numbers (12.5%) of respondents replied that the students frequently learned the vocabulary using semantic maps to remember new English words like Fruit = orange, banana, papaya, etc. On the contrary, more than one-third (41.1%) of the respondents replied that they rarely practiced semantic maps to remember new English words like fruit = orange, banana, papaya, etc. Likewise, nearly half (46.4%) of the respondents responded that the students intermediate learned vocabulary words by using semantic maps to remember new English words like Fruit = orange, banana, papaya. Therefore, students sometimes practiced semantic maps to remember new English words.

Item 11 showed that most (59%) of the respondents responded that the students sometimes learn a new vocabulary using word association. On the other hand, less than a quarter (22.3%) of the participants replied that they rarely utilized to learn vocabulary by practicing word grouping (like questions, issues, problems). As a result, we can generalize that students sometimes practiced learning new vocabularies using word association.

Item 12 displayed that 25.9% of the respondents answered that they rarely learned the vocabulary visualizing the words form to remember. On the contrary, less than half (44.6%) of the respondents responded that they frequently learned the meaning of words by visualizing the words form to remember. Generally, we can deduce that students medium practiced visualizing the words form to remember as a vocabulary learning strategy.

Item 13 revealed that nearly half (48.2%) of the respondents reported that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary using new words in sentences and conversations. On the contrary, one-fourth (25%) of participants responded that the students frequently practiced learning vocabulary using new words in sentences and conversations to remember a new word. Consequently, someone can realize that students frequently practiced using new words in sentences and in conversations to remember the vocabulary.

Item 14, in the same table 2 depicted that half (50%) of the respondents replied that they frequently practiced using the vocabulary section (glossary) in their textbook. Meanwhile, 32.1% of the respondents replied that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary by using the vocabulary section (glossary) in their textbook as a mean score of ($M=3.10$, $SD = 1.33$) proved. Thus, someone can infer that students frequently used the vocabulary learning section (glossary) in their textbook to learn vocabulary.

Table 3
The students' practice of using compensation vocabulary learning strategies

No.	Techniques	No of participants	Responses					M	SD
			Rarely		Some times	Frequently			
			Never	Rarely	Some times	Freque ntly	Almost always		
		112							
15	Using flashcards English words.	No	21	50	19	14	8	2.45	1.16
		%	18.8	44.6	17	12.5	7.1		
16	Using English -Amharic dictionary.	No	10	19	39	30	14	3.16	1.13
		%	8.9	17	34.8	26.8	12.5		
17	Relating the word to my personal experiences	No	16	28	49	13	6	2.68	1.03
		%	14.3	25	43.8	11.6	5.4		
18	Using context clues	No	10	19	21	43	19	3.37	1.20
		%	8.9	17	18.8	38.4	17		
19	Using collocation	No	18	50	30	10	4	2.39	.98
		%	16.1	44.6	26.8	8.9	3.6		
		Grand Mean						2.81	1.1

Key: M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

As table 3 item 15 demonstrated that the majority (63.4%) of the respondents replied that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary using flashcards when they discover new English words. On the contrary, 19.6% of the students answered that they rarely practiced vocabulary-using flashcards when they explored new English words. Hence, one can understand that practicing flashcards to explore new English words was rarely implemented.

Item 16, depicted that 25.9% of the participants replied that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary using the English -Amharic dictionary. Meanwhile, less than half (39.3%) of the students reported that they frequently practiced learning vocabulary using the English-Amharic dictionary. As a result, one can realize that utilizing the English-Amharic dictionary was taken as the major type of vocabulary learning strategy practiced by the students.

In response to item 17, 17% of the respondents answered that they frequently practiced relating the words to their personal experiences to remember the meaning of a new word. On the contrary, 39.3% of the respondents responded that the students rarely practiced relating the word to their personal experiences to remember the meaning of a new word. This implied that relating the words to their personal experiences was rarely practiced.

As indicated in table 3, item 18 revealed that more than half (55.4%) of the respondents responded that they frequently learned the vocabulary using context clues (Like definition, examples, comparison, cause, and effect, etc.).In opposition, 25.9% of the participants answered that they rarely practiced using context clues (Like = definition, example, cause, and effect, etc.). With regarding this, someone who can comprehend utilizing context clues was taken as the most frequent practice of the students' vocabulary learning strategies from compensation strategies.

Concerning item 19, the majority (60.7%) of the students reported that they rarely practiced collocation clues to learn vocabulary. On the other hand, a small number (12.5%) of the respondents replied that they frequently practiced discovering the meaning of new words through collocation (e.g. textbook, homework, group work, etc.). Accordingly, this indicates that the students rarely practiced learning vocabulary through collocation (e.g. textbook, homework, group work, etc.).

Table 4.
Students' practice of using Social vocabulary learning strategies

No.	Techniques	No of participants	Responses					M	SD
			Rarely		Sometimes	Frequently			
			Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Almost always		
		112							
20	Through group work activities (collaboratively).	No	8	17	16	43	28	3.58	1.21
		%	7.1	15.2	14.3	38.4	25		
21	Asking teachers for Amharic translation.	No	10	18	13	37.5	29	3.55	1.27
		%	8.9	16.1	11.6	33.9	25.9		
22	Using Internet, e-mail, chat,	No	9	15	19	42	27	3.56	1.22
		%	8	13.4	17	37.5	24.1		
23	Asking classmates (friends)	No	12	13	17	36	34	3.59	1.31
		%	10.7	11.6	15.2	32.1	30.4		
24	Watching, listening, reading (T.V, brochure, leaflet, poster, etc.)	No	11	13	14	41	33	3.64	1.28
		%	9.8	11.6	12.5	36.6	29.5		
		Grand Mean						3.58	1.25

Key: M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

As shown in Table 4 above, the result of the study in item 20 depicted that less than a quarter (22.3%) of the respondents answered that they rarely learned vocabulary by practicing and learning the meaning of new words through group work activities (collaboratively). On the opposing, more than half (63.4%) of the participants replied that they frequently implemented practicing and learning the meaning of new words through group work activities (collaboratively) with a mean value of (M = 3.58, SD = 1.21). Hence, someone can figure out that practicing and learning the meaning of new words through group work activities (collaboratively) was frequently practiced by students.

Item 21 indicated that exactly a quarter (25%) of the respondents responded that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary by asking teachers for Amharic (L1) translation. Whereas, the majority (62.4%) of the respondents reported that they frequently practiced learning vocabulary by asking the teacher for Amharic or L1 translation. From this, we can understand that the students frequently practiced and learned vocabulary through asking teachers for translation.

As it was observed in table 4, item 22 displayed that 21.4% of the respondents answered that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary using the internet, e-mail, chat, etc. While most (61.6%) of the participants replied that they frequently learned the vocabulary (a word) by using the internet, e-mail, chat, etc. From this, one can also understand that students frequently practiced using the internet, e-mail, and chat, etc. to learn new vocabularies.

Item 23 depicted that 22.3% of the respondents responded that they rarely practiced learning vocabulary asking classmates (friends) to explain the meaning of new words. On the other hand, more than half (62.5%) of the participants reported that they frequently practiced asking classmates (friends) to explain the meaning of new words. This indicated that the students were frequently practicing asking classmates (friends) to explain the meaning of new words.

Item, 24 revealed that (22.4%) of respondents responded that students were rarely learning and practicing the meaning of new words indirectly through watching, listening, reading (TV, brochure, leaflet, poster, etc.). However, the majority (66.1%) of the respondents responded that they frequently practiced learning the meaning of new words indirectly through watching, listening, reading (TV, brochure, leaflet, poster, etc.). Therefore, we

can infer that students frequently practiced learning vocabulary learning and practicing the meaning of new words indirectly through watching, listening, reading (T.V, brochure, leaflet, poster, etc.).

Table 5**Students' practice of Meta-Cognitive vocabulary learning strategies**

No.	Techniques	No of participants	Responses					M	SD
			Rarely		Sometimes	Frequently			
			Never	Rarely	Some times	Frequently	Almost always		
		112							
25	Arranging my vocabulary learning strategies based on the tasks and activities at hand.	No	19	52	28	8	5	2.35	.99
		%	17	46.4	25	7.1	4.5		
26	Evaluating my vocabulary learning progress by using new words in speaking and writing.	No	20	50	20	14	8	2.46	1.13
		%	17.9	44.6	17.9	12.5	7.1		
		Grand Mean						2.40	1.06

Key: M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

As shown in table 5, item 25 indicated that the majority (71.4%) of the respondents replied that they rarely practiced and learned the vocabulary through planning and arranging their vocabulary learning strategies based on tasks and activities at hand. While only a few (11.6%) of the participants answered that they frequently utilized planning and arranging their vocabulary learning strategies based on tasks and activities at hand. This implied that students rarely practiced learning vocabulary through planning and arranging their vocabulary learning strategies based on tasks and activities at hand.

Item 26 revealed that only a few (19.6%) of the respondents responded that they frequently practiced learning the vocabulary by evaluating their vocabulary learning progress using new words in speaking and writing. However, the majority (62.5%) of the respondents reported that they rarely practiced learning a new word by evaluating their vocabulary learning progress by using new words in speaking and writing. This pointed out that the students rarely practiced learning vocabulary by evaluating their vocabulary learning progress and using new words in speaking and writing.

Table 6**Students' practice of using Affective vocabulary learning strategies**

No.	Techniques	No of participants	Responses					M	SD
			Rarely		Sometimes	Frequently			
			Never	Rarely	Some times	Frequently	Almost always		
		112							
27	Reducing my anxiety	No	29	47	17	11	8	2.30	1.16
		%	25.9	42	15.2	9.8	7.1		
28	Motivating myself to read any books, stories, and advertisements, etc.	No	15	40	50	4	3	2.46	.86
		%	13.3	35.7	44.6	3.6	2.7		
		Grand Mean						2.36	1.01

Key=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

As seen in table 6, item 27 displayed that the majority (67.9%) of the respondents answered that they rarely practiced learning new vocabulary words reducing their anxiety and reminding them of their progress in themselves. Nonetheless, only a small number (16.9%) of respondents answered that students frequently practiced learning new vocabulary words by reducing their anxiety by reminding them of their progress. This indicates that students rarely practiced learning a new vocabulary by reducing anxiety.

Item 28 revealed that nearly half (49%) of the respondents answered that the students rarely practiced motivating themselves to read any books, stories, and advertisements, etc to learn vocabularies. Conversely, very few (6.3%) of the respondents responded that learners frequently practiced it with mean value ($M= 2.46$, $SD = .86$). This indicated that students rarely used motivational strategies for learning new vocabularies.

Table 7

Summary on comparisons among vocabulary learning strategies (VLS) in Mean and SD

No.	Vocabulary learning strategy	Mean(M)	SD
1	Cognitive VLS	3.24	1.22
2	Memory VLS	2.83	1.12
3	CompensationVLS	2.81	1.1
4	Social VLS	3.58	1.25
5	Meta-Cognitive VLS	2.40	1.06
6	Affective VLS	2.36	1.01

According to Oxford and Burry-Stock (1995) as cited in Niguse (2013) integrating the mean score of strategy inventory language learning ranges between:

1. 1 to 2.49 → low practice VLS from never- rarely which is “rarely” practiced.
2. 2.5 to 3.49→ medium practice VLS sometimes which is “medium” practiced.
3. 3.5 to 5.0→high practice VLS with frequently- almost always which is “frequently” implemented.

Table 7 above depicted that social vocabulary learning strategies have a maximum mean value of ($M=3.58$, $SD=1.25$). The practice rate of social strategies as described above is higher than cognitive, memory, and compensation strategies. However, students' practice of cognitive strategies were seemed medium since it has the value of ($M=3.24$, $SD=1.22$). Besides this, students' practice of vocabulary learning strategies of memory strategies was also medium practiced since the mean value was ($M=2.83$, $SD=1.12$). However, the practice of Meta-cognitive and affective strategies as demonstrated above was less practiced than the direct strategies and the indirect ones (social strategies). Hence, these strategies were rarely practiced. It was less practiced than the direct strategies and indirect ones like social and meta-cognitive. To wind up, social vocabulary learning strategies were stood first that students most frequently practiced. Cognitive, memory, and compensation vocabulary learning strategies were medium practiced while meta-cognitive and affective vocabulary learning strategies were rarely practiced.

Challenges affecting students' practice of vocabulary learning strategies

The majority of the participants responded that the major challenges students faced in the practice of vocabulary learning strategies were lack of vocabulary knowledge, lack of intrinsic motivation, lack of experience to utilize vocabulary learning strategies, lack of using appropriate context clues, unable to use prior knowledge, and unable to practice beyond cognitive (Meta-cognitive) activities. Moreover, the respondents also answered that learners faced external challenges to practice and learn vocabulary when using vocabulary learning strategies in the EFL classes were like teachers' traditional method of teaching, tasks, unclear curriculum instruction, and complexity of vocabulary tasks.

From the above responses, we can infer that lack of practice and experience to develop appropriate vocabulary learning strategies, lack of self-motivation to equip themselves, limitation of linguistic items or word power, lack of awareness of suitable vocabulary learning strategies, fear of making mistakes were internal factors in the practice of using vocabulary learning strategies to discover the meaning of new words in the EFL classes. On the other hand, traditional ways of teaching, lack of EFL teachers' supports in teaching appropriate vocabulary learning strategies practice, uninterested curriculum designing, unclear instruction, the size and the complexity of the tasks, and lack of genuine communication, etc. were considered as external hinders.

4.4. Analysis Teachers' Semi-Structured Interview

Teachers were interviewed to justify the major vocabulary learning strategies students prefer to use learning new vocabularies. Most teachers responded that:

the vocabulary learning strategies students practice frequently were through group work activities (collaboratively), asking classmates (friends), group work activities, watching T.V, listening to the radio, reading brochures, leaflet, a poster which is written in the English language.

However, few teachers asserted that students frequently practice using cognitive strategies. In conclusion, we can infer that learners practiced (utilized) social learning strategies to know the meaning of new words in EFL class since the strategy has taken as the modern ways of vocabulary learning strategies like the inductive method of vocabulary learning strategies using various techniques.

Teachers were also interviewed to state the major factors hindering the practice of learning a new vocabulary using vocabulary learning strategies. All-in-one asserted that:

lack of EFL teachers support to practice appropriate vocabulary learning strategies, lack of self-encouragement to equip the students themselves with lexical knowledge, lack of experience to use appropriate vocabulary learning strategies, absence of good school environment, as well as little exposure and negative attitude towards English language learning using the modern (inductive method) of vocabulary learning strategies, were the major obstacles hindering learning new vocabularies.

Therefore, we can generalize that there are students' and teachers'-related factors hindering students' practice of learning vocabulary.

4.5. Analysis of students Focus Group Discussion

Nine students i.e. 3 students from low achievers, 3 students' medium achievers, and 3 students from high scorers were selected from their first semester results purposively to get desirable results for FGDs. To begin with, students were interrogated to state the types of vocabulary learning strategies they used to learn new vocabulary frequently.

Most of the participants from higher achiever (H), medium achiever (M), and low achiever (L) argued that they used context clues, asking the teachers, translating English to Amharic language (L1), using semantic maps, flashcards, glossary as well as practiced collaborative as a technique to learn new vocabularies. However, only a few respondents from H, M, and L agreed that the students practiced learning the meaning of new words by using music, lowering anxiety, and taking risks wisely as effective learning strategies in the least frequency.

In conclusion, FGDs responses revealed that the majority of the students practiced social categories of vocabulary learning strategies to discover the meaning of new words in EFL classes frequently compared to the other strategies.

Secondly, students were asked to mention major problems they face when they are learning English vocabulary through vocabulary learning strategies.

The majority of the respondents from higher, medium, and lower agreed that major problems learners faced when learning vocabulary in EFL class through using the strategies were lack of word power, in the appropriate use of vocabulary learning strategies to learn words, anxiety, and unable to use the inductive method of vocabulary learning to know the new words and difficult words in the glossary. Furthermore, all-in-one stated that they have had little awareness of various vocabulary learning strategies such as memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies. Similarly, most of the respondents argued that they have faced challenges from teachers' method of vocabulary-teaching and students' lack of experience to utilize efficient vocabulary learning strategies in the EFL classes. More to the point, most of the students replied that the students' lack of word power caused the learners to use inappropriate vocabulary learning strategies in the EFL classes.

By and large, we can conclude that the lack of awareness to practice appropriate vocabulary learning strategies, lack of vocabulary knowledge, inappropriate use of vocabulary learning strategies, fear of making mistakes, lack of EFL teachers help in teaching the strategies and lack of experience in using the strategies were the major obstacles challenging students to practice vocabulary learning strategies.

Thirdly, students were asked to state vocabulary learning strategies that are frequently used and least practiced in EFL classes.

The majority of them responded that creating the structure for input and output (e.g. taking notes; high lighting), guessing intelligently and cooperating with others were the most frequently practiced vocabulary learning strategies to learn vocabularies in EFL class, but the remaining creating mental linkages (e.g. grouping; associating/ elaborating), practicing and encouraging one-self were rarely used. Meanwhile, only a few of the participants argued that meta-cognitive and affective were least utilized.

To make it brief, the responses of the FGDs participants revealed that the majority of the students practiced cooperating with others (cooperating with peers, or proficiency users of the teaching language) which was the most frequent vocabulary learning strategy. On the other hand, most of the respondents argued that Meta-Cognitive and effective vocabulary learning strategies were the least practiced.

V. Discussion of results

In the discussion, the research questions were addressed by triangulating the results obtained from the different data analyses. In this part of the study, an attempt has been made to integrate, explain and triangulate the results of the data gathered through the three instruments to answer the basic research questions. In addition, the findings of the study were high lightened and presented in connection with the literature review.

The first research question was on discovering the major types of vocabulary learning strategies that students use most frequently and least frequently in the practice of learning vocabulary in EFL class. The finding obtained from the questionnaires proved that social strategies were the first and the most frequently practiced vocabulary-learning strategies to discover the meaning of new words in the EFL classes. Social strategy vocabulary learning strategies gained the first rank of all the categories. In this regard, Wenden and Rubin (1987) declared that social vocabulary learning strategies activities promoted learners' appropriateness to be exposed to the target language. It was also supported by the results gained from the teachers' semi-structured interviews and the students' responses to FGD in the qualitative data. However, the find of this study was contrary to Setegn (2007), Getnet (2008), and Niguse (2013). Cognitive strategies were claimed as being the second rank practiced by the participants of the study. Out of these techniques, word formation and taking a note in the class in English were reported as the most frequently practiced strategies to discover the meaning of new words in the EFL classes. Nonetheless, the finding is different from Setegn's (2007. According to Stein, memory, cognitive, and determination strategies were used by the subjects more frequently. Along this side, memory strategies took the third rank with mean Value ($M = 2.83$, $SD=1.12$). Students practiced learning meanings by studying the spelling of a word and its pronunciation to remember the meaning of a word, guessing the meaning of a word by using available pictures or gestures" rarely practiced. Therefore, memory strategy has been ranked third most actively practiced of the others. The findings revealed that the compensation strategy took the fourth rank of all the other strategies. The finding obtained from the FGDs and interviews confirmed that compensation strategy was sometimes practiced. Besides, the findings showed that Meta-cognitive and affective strategies were rarely implemented, and ranked fifth and sixth respectively. Of all other strategies, affective strategies were the least practiced strategies.

The second research question was on assessing the major challenges students face while learning vocabulary using vocabulary learning strategies in EFL class. The students encountered both internal and external challenges while learning vocabulary using vocabulary learning strategies. The findings obtained from the questionnaires, interview and FGDs revealed that students faced major challenges like lack of experience, lack of motivation, the poor practice of using vocabulary learning strategies, bad habit of reading, fear of making mistakes, lack of vocabulary, and limited knowledge to practice using vocabulary learning strategies in EFL classes were the internal or students' related challenges. Conversely, an inappropriate method of teaching, the size of the tasks being too difficult or easy, unclear instruction, and limitation of sources were external challenges as well. In line with Macaro (2010) supported that learners faced internal factors including lack of vocabulary, lack of experience in vocabulary learning strategies, age, attitude, motivation of the learners, personality, hemisphere specialization, and poor practice of vocabulary learning strategies during the EFL learning activities to discover the meaning of new words in the EFL class. Moreover, Schmitt (2007) also claimed the students' lexical knowledge is considered as central to the communicative approach, so learning words for beings rich in

vocabulary and forwarded to equip the students in using appropriate vocabulary learning strategies in the EFL classes is critical.

VI. Conclusions

Considering the research questions and the findings obtained, the following conclusions were drawn. To make it brief, social strategies were the most frequently practiced vocabulary learning strategies that students prefer to learn new vocabularies. Memory, cognitive and compensation strategies took the second rank and were medium utilized by the students. However, meta-cognitive and affective strategies were rarely practiced by participants at all. The findings obtained from the questionnaires, interview, and focus group discussions revealed that students have faced challenges like lack of awareness to practice better strategies of vocabulary learning, lack of vocabulary knowledge, inappropriate use of vocabulary learning strategies, fear of making mistakes, lack of EFL teachers' help in teaching the strategies, and lack of experience in using the strategies.

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